

A Study on Constructs Influencing Women Investor Behaviour in Stock Market: A Cross Country Research Survey

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ABSTRACT

The 20th century has witnessed significant advancement in technology, healthcare and thus human life more compatible with nature to co-exist. The progress observed can be attributed and evaluated by various indicators such as GDP, happiness index, Human Development Index etc. In this economic development, the contribution of women has also been very significant. In India, the economic advancement can definitely be attributed in the recent years to participation of the women in labour workforce. The improved working environment, financial independence and financial literacy observed over the last several decades has facilitated in participation of women in labour workforce like never before. With this financial independence, women have been observed to take decisions on financial freedom. Behavioural finance is the branch of study which attempts to describe the financial decisions taken by investors by combining psychology theory and conventional financial theory, which is used to understand how emotions and personality traits influence individual investors' behaviour. Many women investors find investments to be captivating because they can participate in the decision making process and see the results of their choice. Recent studies on the behaviour of women investors have shown that they do not act in a rational manner which is aligned with general literature on investment decisions. During the decision making process they exhibit various emotions like anxiety, fear, happiness, greed etc. which in turn have emotional impact on their decision making ability. The present study aims to review the research studies and literature to gain knowledge about key constructs that influence investment behaviour in different countries and the ways these constructs impact on investment decision making process among women investors in stock market.

Keywords: Investments, behavioural finance, constructs, women investors.

INTRODUCTION

Economy of any country is determined by investments leading to capital formation. Savings result in investments. In India, the household sector occupies important place as far as savings is concerned in comparison to industrial sectors, whether it is private or public. The level of equity market participation of the women investors has been increasing over the past few years. Investment is the deployment of capital for earning profitable return in future. There is a great prominence on investment for being the primary instrument of economic growth and development for a country. Women, in general are savers according to the Association of Bankers report.

Equity market otherwise called stock market is a public entity for trading shares of a particular company at an agreed price. Supply and demand in the stock market is affected by various factors that in turn affect the price of the stock. Investment decisions are still found to be complicated as there are various determinants to be considered to choose equity or a stock to invest in or trade into. These socio- economic, demographic, psychological, economical and attitudinal factors act as key drivers for investment decisions.

Behavioural finance introduces the the application of psychological and economic principles for the improvement of individual financial decision making process. Shefrin (2000) in his book titled "Beyond Greed and Fear" conveyed the key concept that people are imperfect processors of information and are usually biased, commit mistakes and have perceptual problems. Currently, no unified theory of behavioural finance exists. With a changing scenario, women has started actively participating in investing their surplus money, though it all depends upon the various factors such as degree of their risk taking capability, influence of family members, we can categorize majority of the factors into key constructs demographic, physiological, economic, social and others.

An increasing number of research studies found that women invest their money more conservatively than their male counterparts a finding that is generally consistent with the common wisdom of financial services providers. Although there is number of literatures on types of gender differences in financial decision making, examination of differences in investment behaviour is a relatively new way for research. The existence of gender differences raises important questions for public policy. Although there are obvious implications for the overall financial well-being of women in retirement, interventions can be more effectively designed with better understanding of the underlying causes of observed investment patterns.

Objectives:

- To determine the various constructs influencing women investors' behaviour as investigated by several researchers in different countries.
- To provide comprehensive review of studies on women investors' behaviour in the financial investments with particular reference to stock investments.

Methodology:

The present paper is a review paper. Various papers on constructs, factors and determinants of investment behaviour across different countries have been taken for the review.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Sundaram, Krishnan, 2010) examined that the judgement heuristics like rationality or irrationality of the investment pattern and behaviour will enable the investor to act with caution as the consequences are likely to affect the asset value, lifestyle, relationship with others and social interaction. Investors in various places acknowledge the role of emotions in investment decision making and their empirical results suggested that the demographic factors influence the investors' investment decision.

(Dev Prasad, Shollapur, 2014) highlighted that the Indian women investors as emotional decision Makers, this study expects to contribute to the literature by focusing on the investment behaviour of Indian women investors in what is predominantly still a male dominated market, whether the human emotions of greed, fear, love, and disbelief influence the decision making process of women investors considering investment opportunities in the Indian stock market.

(Engin Demirel et al., 2011) studied the interaction between demographic and financial behavioral factors in investment decisions. The study was carried to find the impact of demographic factors influencing individual investors' behavior. It showed that gender interacts with five financial behavioral factors i.e. Overreaction, herding, cognitive bias, irrational thinking, and overconfidence and the level of individual savings interacts with only four of the financial behavioral factors viz; overreaction, herding, cognitive bias, and irrational thinking.

Ngoc (2014) investigated behavioural factors influencing the decisions of individual investors at the Securities Companies in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. He collects data from 188 individual investors with a response rate of 63%. There are five behavioural factors of individual investors at the Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange: Herding, Market, Prospect, Overconfidence gamble's fallacy, and Anchoring-ability bias. The herding factor includes behavioural dimensions: following the decisions of the other investors (buying and selling, choice of trading stocks, volume of trading stocks). The market factor consists of dimensions: price changes, market information. The prospect factor consists of dimensions: loss aversion, regret aversion, and mental accounting. The heuristic dimensions are grouped into two factors: overconfidence-gamble's fallacy and anchoring-ability bias. He recommends that investors should consider carefully before investment, but should not care too much about the prior loss for later investment. Besides, the investors should not reduce their regret in investment by avoiding selling decreasing stocks and selling increasing ones.

(Mohammad Shafi, 2014) concluded that there are numerous determinants that influence the individual investor's behaviour in stock market. Some factors influence majorly while other have slight role in influencing the behaviour of an individual investor. The factors can be grouped into demographic, economic, social, and psychological in nature. The most common determinants that have a significant impact on the investors' behaviour are herding, over-reaction, cognitive bias, irrational thinking, confidence (over or under), gender, age, income, education, risk factor, dividends, influence of people's opinion (friends or family), past performance of the company, accounting information, ownership structure, bonus payments, expected corporate earnings, get rich quick.

(Tabassum, Pardhasaradhi, 2012) found that investment decision process is considered critical decision for every investor, especially when investing in equities as it involves high risk and the returns are not certain. While choosing a particular stock to make an investment, 40 attributes have been identified that influence the investor buying decision

process. The most influencing attributes were identified and ranked based on the frequency of highly important rating given by the investor. To identify factors influencing the behaviour of Indian individual equity investors the current study has applied factor analysis. After applying factor analysis it was found that all the 40 attributes are reduced to the following ten factors namely Individual Eccentric, Wealth Maximization, Risk Minimization, Brand Perception, Social Responsibility, Financial Expectation, Accounting information, Government & Media, Economic Expectation and Advocate recommendation factors.

(Schmidt & Sevak, 2006) examined that women's investment has historically been lower than men for several reasons, including Social and various demographic concerns. However, the differences continue to be significant even after controlling for individual Characteristics.

(Banumathy, Azhagaiah, 2016) admits that there is a significant difference between male and female investors on awareness of stock market investment; there is a significant difference among the age, educational and occupational groups with respect to awareness; there is also a significant difference among the investors of different age and occupational groups, in respect of awareness.

Constructs influencing women investor behaviour:

- **Demographic Factors:** Investor's gender, age, marital status, education, income, occupation etc.
- **Lifestyle Characteristics:** Personal ability, confidence level and dependency level of investors.
- **Psychological Influences:** Desires, goals, biases and emotions that guide the Investor's decision.
- **Risk Bearing Capacity:** Parameters of safety, liquidity, capital appreciation, return and riskcoverage.
- **Personal Values:** Socially and religiously expressive characteristics.
- **Accounting Information:** Information about Stock market, Expected Corporate Earnings, Financial Position, and Dividend Paid, Expected Dividend and the Past Performance.
- **Advocate Recommendation:** Advice or recommendation from the Broker, Family members, Friends and Stock holder/ expert.
- **Personal Financial Needs:** Diversification needs, Easy availability of the funds whenever needed, Need to minimize the risk and loss and maximize the return.
- **Behavioural factors:** Overreaction, herding, cognitive bias, irrational thinking, and overconfidence
- **Other Constructs:** Inflation, Social Responsibility.

CONCLUSION

From the review of above literatures, it can be summarized that there are numerous constructs that influence the women investor's behaviour in stock market. Some factors influence majorly while other have trivial role in influencing the behaviour of awomen investor. The constructs can be grouped into demographic, economic, social, behavioural and psychological in nature. The most common constructs that have a significant impact on the investors' behaviour are herding, over-reaction, cognitive bias, irrational thinking, confidence (over or under), gender, age, income, education, risk factor, dividends, influence of friends or family opinion, past performance of the company. On the other hand there are several factors which were found uncommon in various studies conducted across different countries such as Financial knowledge or literacy, knowledge about Stock trading and portfolio, expected losses financial markets, diversification, tax concernsof an investment and inflation.

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